

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

ШЕТ ТІЛІНДЕ СЫНИ ОҚУДЫ ОҚЫТУДА САНДЫҚ ҚҰРАЛДАРДЫ ПАЙДАЛАНУДЫҢ ӘДІСТЕМЕЛІК НЕГІЗДЕМЕСІ

Абдуллаева А.

Сеньор лектор

Алматы технологиялық университеті

Базарова Д.

Сеньор лектор

Алматы технологиялық университеті

Орынтаева Н.

Лектор ассистент

Алматы технологиялық университеті

Жазира Ә.

Лектор ассистент

Алматы технологиялық университеті

METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK OF USING DIGITAL TOOLS IN TEACHING CRITICAL READING IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Abdullayeva A.

Senior Lecturer

Almaty Technological University

Bazarova D.

Senior Lecturer

Almaty Technological University

Oryntayeva N.

Assistant Lecturer

Almaty Technological University

Aubakir Zh.

Assistant Lecturer

Almaty Technological University

Андатпа

Мақала шет тілінде сыни оқуды оқытуға сандық құралдарды енгізудің әдістемелік негіздемесіне арналған. Білім берудің сандық трансформациясы және ағылшын тіліндегі ғылыми ақпарат көлемінің өсуі жағдайында зерттеу сандық құралдарды көмекші емес, когнитивті күшейткіш ретінде қолдану тұжырымдамасын негіздейді. Авторлар сандық ресурстарды іріктеу үшін критерийлер жүйесін және олардың когнитивтік функцияларына негізделген құралдар типологиясын ұсынып, олардың қолданылуын мәтінге дейінгі, мәтіндік және мәтіннен кейінгі кезеңдер бойынша ұйымдастыруды ұсынады, бұл талдау дағдыларын, ақпаратты тексеруді және сыни тұрғыдан ойлауды дамытуға бағытталған.

Abstract

The article addresses the methodological framework for integrating digital tools into teaching critical reading in a foreign language to students of non-linguistic universities. In the context of digital transformation and the increasing volume of scientific information in English, the study justifies the concept of digital tools as cognitive enhancers rather than auxiliary aids. The authors propose a system of criteria for selecting digital resources and a typology of tools based on their cognitive functions, structuring their use across the pre-text, text, and post-text stages of work to develop analytical skills, information verification, and critical thinking.

Түйін сөздер: сыни оқу, сандық құралдар, шет тілін оқыту, когнитивті күшейткіштер, әдістемелік негіздеме.

Keywords: critical reading, digital tools, foreign language teaching, cognitive enhancers, methodological framework.

Introduction. The intensification of the digitisation of higher education and the avalanche-like growth of scientific knowledge, represented mainly in English, necessitate a review of existing pedagogical approaches to developing critical reading skills in students of non-language disciplines. The dominance of English-language sources in global scientific discourse is trans-

forming the requirements for graduates: the competitiveness of a specialist is determined not only by their foreign language communication skills, but also by their ability to critically reflect on professional texts.

In this context, the digital environment creates fundamentally new didactic opportunities, allowing us to overcome the "paper" paradigmatic approach to teaching reading. Despite the widespread penetration of

digital solutions into academic practice, their potential for the targeted development of critical, rather than general language or technical, text-working skills remains unsystematic and methodologically unclaimed, creating a gap between technological offerings and pedagogical expediency.

The practice of teaching foreign languages in non-linguistic universities demonstrates that students face a range of difficulties when analysing authentic scientific texts. These difficulties range from decoding the surface meaning to the inability to conduct a substantive examination of the research, identify its methodological conflicts, hidden assumptions, and weaknesses in argumentation.

Literature review. The modern educational paradigm is undergoing fundamental changes associated with the transition to digital didactics, where digital tools are no longer an optional element but have become an integral part of students' cognitive and communicative activities. As R. R. Khizbullina rightly notes, the integration of technology contributes to the formation of systematic thinking through the possibilities of multidimensional visualisation and analysis of

complex interrelationships, with a synergistic effect achieved through the competent combination of innovative approaches with classical teaching methods. In turn, the study by I. Compagnoni and F. Fazzi emphasises the role of developing digital mediation skills, which are formed within specially organised learning communities where students collectively explore and test the functionality of digital services to solve specific educational tasks.

Thus, the digital transformation of education determines not just the mechanical introduction of technological innovations, but the need for a profound reworking of pedagogical methods and the formation of a new culture of educational interaction based on the principles of collaboration, critical evaluation of digital content, and self-regulated learning.

Given the multifaceted didactic potential of digital technologies, their effective application in the educational process, particularly in the development of critical reading skills, requires their systematisation according to functional and pedagogical criteria.

Table 1

Categories of digital tools

Category	Characteristics	Examples
Analytical tools	Promote the development of critical information processing skills; enable quantitative and qualitative analysis of texts, identifying the frequency of lexical units and semantic connections	Voyant Tools
Interactive tools	Enable collaborative annotation of texts and organisation discussion organisation, promoting the development of critical thinking through collaborative learning	Hypothesis, Perusall
Graphical tools For data representation	Stimulate thought processes by converting text data into graphical diagrams and models	MindMeister, Canva
Adaptive systems	Enable the implementation of individual educational pathways for each learner, taking into account their language proficiency and cognitive characteristics	IBM Watson, ChatGPT

The current stage of development of higher education is characterised by a profound transformation of its methodological foundations, driven by digital transformation. In the context of foreign language training, this is reflected in the transition from adapting existing methodologies to a fundamental restructuring of the didactic model as a whole. As substantiated in the work of Yu. V. Eremin and his colleagues, this process necessitates comprehensive methodological restructuring, including the revision and design of new interactive teaching formats that are adequate to the challenges of the digital age.

The key vector of this restructuring is the targeted development of digital competencies and meta-subject skills (soft skills). L. A. Lazutova and co-authors empirically prove that the synergistic effect of combining interactive pedagogical strategies and targeted digital tools creates a unique educational ecosystem that contributes to the formation of not only narrowly professional but also universal competencies that are in de-

mand in the modern labour market. This thesis is further specified in the study by S. V. Gubik and E. R. Shakirova, who identify the structure of digital competencies, highlighting information literacy, digital communication, creative content creation and, particularly significant for our study, critical thinking as a system-forming element.

Thus, the integration of digital tools leads not to a simple expansion of the traditional methodological arsenal, but to the formation of a holistic hybrid educational environment. This environment synthesises the advantages of face-to-face interaction (direct dialogue, emotional feedback) and the flexibility of online formats (asynchrony, personalisation, access to unlimited resources), creating a new quality of educational process.

Methods. The methodological framework of this study is based on a synthesis of Russian, Kazakhstani and foreign scientific thought covering three key areas: the digital transformation of education, methods for developing critical reading in a foreign language, and the

integration of digital technologies into pedagogical practice.

The theoretical and methodological foundation includes the following works:

In the field of digital didactics and the transformation of the educational space: the concepts of R. R. Khizbullina, B. Dasha and R. Moreno, which were supplemented by research by Kazakhstani scientists such as A.K. Kairbaeva, who analysed the didactic potential of digital platforms in the national context.

In the field of foreign language teaching methodology in non-linguistic universities: approaches by I. Compagnoni and F. Fazzi, Yu. V. Eremina, L. A. Lazutova, as well as scientific works by Kazakhstani specialists (e.g., I. M. Makarikhina) researching issues of foreign language communicative competence formation in multilingual environments.

In the field of psychological and pedagogical foundations of critical reading: the works of A. K. Kairbaeva, T. M. Fomenko, M. K. Khasan, which made it possible to consider the cognitive mechanisms of critical text perception from an interdisciplinary perspective.

In the field of critical thinking development in linguistics and pedagogy: models by S. V. Chernyshov and A. N. Shamov, A. A. Filippova, as well as the views of Kazakhstani authors on the structure of critical thinking as a meta-subject educational outcome.

During the research, a multi-level analysis of scientific literature was carried out, which included:

1. Systematisation of modern domestic and foreign educational practices using digital tools for the development of analytical skills.

2. Identification and conceptualisation of key didactic contradictions and unrealised advantages of digital learning.

3. Comparative evaluation of the results of experimental studies in the field of foreign language education technology.

To solve the set tasks, a set of qualitative analysis methods was applied, including content analysis and synthesis of scientific concepts, bibliographic analysis to establish interdisciplinary connections, as well as inductive and deductive methods to verify hypotheses and construct a theoretical model. This comprehensive approach ensured the representativeness and reliability of the theoretical conclusions.

Results. Designing a pedagogically effective digital environment for developing critical analysis skills in foreign-language texts requires a well-thought-out strategy for selecting technological solutions. Teachers should be guided not by intuitive preferences, but by a strict set of criteria that ensures that the chosen tool acts as a catalyst for cognitive processes rather than a digital surrogate for them.

The proposed system is based on the principle of functional and didactic correspondence. Its implementation ensures a direct correlation between the operational characteristics of a digital resource and the step-by-step formation of specific operations of critical text perception, such as deconstruction of argumentation, verification of sources, and synthesis of information.

Table 2

Criteria for selecting digital tools	
Criteria	Recommendations
Compliance didactic objectives	Tools should support methods that promote the development of critical thinking: analysis, comparison, discussion, and the formulation of reasoned conclusions. It is important to have tools for working with scientific articles
Interactivity and feedback	Opportunities for discussion and joint analysis of texts. The presence of a built-in chat, commenting functions, text annotation and feedback from the teacher
Flexibility and adaptability	The digital tool should adapt to the level of student preparation. Availability of tools for independent work: text highlighting, note-taking, structure visualisation
Technical reliability and accessibility	Stable operation, connection quality, availability of a mobile version and technical support. Ability to integrate with other educational resources and platforms
Motivational potential	Tools that help increase interest in learning and cognitive activity

Digital tools as a catalyst for the development of critical reading

Modern digital technologies are fundamentally changing the landscape of critical reading skills development in a foreign language. The transformation affects the very essence of the educational process — there is a shift from reproductive assimilation of information to research activity, where the student becomes an active subject of cognition. The digital environment stimulates the development of academic autonomy, developing students' ability to independently search for

information sources, verify them and systematically comprehend them.

The methodology for working with foreign-language scientific texts is based on the integration of technological solutions into the structure of analytical activity. Critical reading is revealed as a multidimensional intellectual process that goes beyond a superficial understanding of content. It includes in-depth analysis of argumentation models, deconstruc-

tion of implicit layers of meaning, assessment of the reliability of sources, and the formation of reasoned evaluative judgements.

Technological support is implemented through a system of step-by-step interaction with text material. At the preparatory stage, digital tools allow background knowledge to be updated and semantic guidelines to be formed. During the analysis process, technological solutions provide interactive annotation and visualisation of logical connections. The final phase involves the use of platforms for organising reflective activities and developing academic communication skills.

Conclusion. The study allows us to conclude that the integration of digital tools into the process of teaching critical reading of scientific texts in a foreign language is not just a technological update, but a fundamental transformation of the educational paradigm. Digital technologies act as cognitive enhancers, contributing to the formation of systematic analytical thinking and the development of academic autonomy in students of technical specialities.

The effectiveness of this transformation is determined by compliance with key methodological conditions. First, it is necessary to carefully select digital solutions in accordance with the tasks of each stage of working with the text. Secondly, it is essential to take into account the level of digital literacy of students. Thirdly, it is necessary to systematically introduce technologies into the educational process, excluding their fragmentary use.

Specialised platforms that enable interactive work with text based on modern approaches, such as the INSERT method, demonstrate particular methodological potential. Such solutions purposefully develop a set of critical analysis skills, including the identification of key concepts, the deconstruction of argumentative structures, the interpretation of implicit meanings, and the verification of information reliability.

The developed system of criteria for selecting digital tools ensures the targeted development of higher-order cognitive operations and the formation of meta-subject competencies necessary for successful professional activity in the context of the digital transformation of science and education. Structured strategies

for working with text confirm that digital tools optimise cognitive load and enhance analytical processes, contributing to the development of critical reading competence as the basis for the academic and professional mobility of modern specialists.

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